

**SCIENTIFIC AND THEORETICAL BASIS OF FORMING SPEAKING
SKILLS OF ENGLISH STUDENTS THROUGH MNEMONIC EXERCISES**

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Annotation: *The article provides information about mnemonic exercises aimed at developing the lexical competence of students of higher educational institutions in English, and their meaning.*

Key words: *mnemonics, speech skills, communication, lexical units, semantic analysis, linguistic data.*

In the world education system, the need to use modern pedagogical approaches in the formation of students' speaking skills is increasing. In particular, in the teaching of foreign languages, new approaches are emerging, which serve to improve the mastery of the studied language by means of mnemonic exercises. It is considered to be especially important to form the speaking skills of English language students by means of mnemonic exercises, as it contributes to the formation of the ability to establish a successful relationship.

The essence and content of modern concepts of English language teaching in our country, integration in the educational process, issues of teaching foreign languages and innovations in the learning process G.H. Bakieva, L.T. Akhmedova, J.J. Jalolov, T.K. Sattarov, M. Djusupov, D.U. Khashimova, Kh.D. Paluanova, A.A. Nasirov, K. Sh. Muradkasimova, Conducted by F.M.Rashidova, S.A.Nazarova, A.B.Rakhmonov, S.N.Abdullaeva, A.Kh.Zhoraev, D.M.Djuraev, D.A.Tadjibaeva, S.A.Ziyaeva.

Ways of forming speech skills in foreign language teaching are researched by U.K. Nosirova, N.V. Obukhov, R.F. Gabdulkhakova and a number of other scientists, as well as E.Y. Malushko, S.V. Samarskaya, A.G. Solomatina, P.V. Sisoyeva, T.L. Gerasimenko, T.V. Kolesova and other scientists, also the works of foreign researchers such as Sally Ashton-Hay, Masudul Hassan, R. Chakrakodi, Jeremy Harmer, R. Roberts are dedicated.[1:11]

A large number of scientific and practical researches are focused on the formation of speaking skills for English language teaching and determining their evaluation criteria. However, until now, the method of forming students' speaking skills in English by means of mnemonic exercises in the continuous education system has not been researched, so it remains open for theoretical analysis and experimental research.[2:14]

Theoretically, the laws of mnemonics achieved special development in the 19th century. A large number of scientific and practical studies are aimed at the formation of speaking skills for English language teaching and determining their evaluation criteria. However, until now, the method of forming students' speaking skills in English by means of mnemonic exercises in the continuous education system has not been researched, so it remains open for theoretical analysis and experimental research.[3]

Mnemonics (Greek: μνημονικός "mnēmonikos" - the art of remembering) is a system of methods that facilitate recall and expand memory by creating artificial associations.

The term mnemonics comes from the Greek words: mneme-memory and techne-art, craft. According to Kozarenko's definition, mnemonics is "a well-founded internal writing system, a direct recording in the brain of connections between visual images to mark important elements of memorized information." [6]

Mnemonic technology as a pedagogical direction developed by M.A. Ziganov, A.K. Kolechenko, Matyugin, T. B. Polyanskaya, I. Rybnikova, E and others. Pedagogical mnemonics, along with mnemonic technology, is a technology that allows us to quickly remember information, unlike psychological, in other words, it is a comfortable environment to help students learn and create a program using various methods of memory development.[4]

In mnemonics, the ancient Greeks discovered that images of the imagination can be used to memorize a lot of information, and the science that studies such techniques was called mnemonics. This book describes the secrets of people with "super" memory, types of mnemonics, methods of using them to remember digital and textual information, names of people and other necessary information, historical dates, and ways to learn foreign languages correctly. This knowledge is useful for students to master various subjects and learn foreign languages easily.

It is known that the effective memorization and reproduction of a certain material by a person is related to the forms of memory.[5:13]. According to the participation of the will in the processes of memorizing and reproduction of material, memory is divided into voluntary and involuntary. This offer can be viewed as follows:

First, the learner has the ability to automatically perform a special mnemonic task (memorization, recognition, storage or reproduction) without much effort. However, memorizing, remembering, and improving the memory of students is the most effective way to use mnemonic exercises.

Mnemonics, the art of memorization, mnemonics - total tricks and methods that facilitate memory and increase memory by making artificial associations. Thus, a mnemonic is a type of coded formulae that you can easily conjure up images related to your subconscious mind or another link in this chain.

From the point of view of mnemonic memory, educational activity is the independence of efforts to memorize the material, conscious attention to the memorization of the material, and a consistent and deep understanding of the educational material is a must. Therefore, if this material is included in the target content of this action, it may be inadvertently recalled. However, what is not included in the target content of the act of voluntary memorization is remembered worse than independent memorization directed at this material. All this depends, first of all, on how the movement of the subject to be memorized is organized and what it is directed towards. Therefore, involuntary memorization may not only be a matter of work, it can be regulated indirectly. Thus, from a pedagogical point of view, the most important task is to organize the learning process so that important material is remembered by students, and he remembers it not only when working with this material. The laws of memory activity described above are also reflected in the memorization of lexical units of a foreign language.

Mnemonic memorization consists of four stages:(1 fig)

Encoding to images → memorization (combining two pictures) → memorizing the sequence → function in memory

Mnemonics is a set of special techniques and methods that facilitate the memorization of necessary information and increase memory capacity by forming associations (connections): replacing abstract objects and facts with concepts and ideas that have a visual, auditory or kinesthetic image, objects with information in memory. connecting, memorizing, secondly, such a task in the student necessarily requires the process of voluntary memorization or reproduction. (2fig)

The most popular classification of mnemonic techniques:

1. Letter-sound mnemonics (the presence of the same letters and sounds, memorization to create a partial similarity to the necessary information);
2. Rhymes (creating consonant pairs of words or phrases, memorizing the material they contain);
3. Method of association (finding bright, unusual images, connecting with some memorized information);
4. Schematic-pictorial mnemonics (use of various schemes, table, picture, pictures for better memorization);
5. Letter-sound mnemonics (the presence of the same letters and sounds, memorization to create a partial similarity to the necessary information).

As a conclusion, it should be noted that mnemonics are important in the formation of the skills of reading, writing, listening and speaking, using the associative, schematic, rhyming method to master English lessons well for students of the A1 level.

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